

Electrochemical studies on some 4-(4'-sulphonamoyl)hydrazono-3-methyl-2-isoxazolin-5-ones

Rajeev Jain*, P. Padmaja, M. K. Shrivastava and Seema Gupta

School of Studies in Chemistry, Jiwaji University, Gwalior-474 011, India

Manuscript received 21 January 1999, revised 2 August 1999, accepted 13 August 1999

Electrochemical reduction of 4-(4'-sulphonamoyl)hydrazono-3-methyl-2-isoxazolin-5-ones has been studied over a wide pH range at dme and GC electrodes. These compounds give single, four-electron wave/peak corresponding to the reduction of hydrazono group. On the basis of polarography, cyclic voltammetry, coulometry and product identification, a reaction mechanism is proposed for the reduction of hydrazono group.

Polarographic behaviour of hydrazono compounds has been subject of many investigations¹. However, a literature survey reveals the absence of systematic electrochemical study on sulphonamoylhydrazonoisoxazolin-5-ones, a class of compounds having medicinal importance. This paper deals with the electrochemical behaviour of 4-(4'-sulphonamoyl)

hydrazono-3-methyl-2-isoxazolin-5-ones (A) at dme and GC electrodes.

Results and Discussion

All the sulphonamoylhydrazonoisoxazolin-5-ones (Table 1) exhibited single, four-electron, well-defined wave/peak in the pH range 2.5–11.0.

Polarography: On the basis of the number of electrons involved in the electrode process and the potential at which reduction is taking place, it may be concluded that the polarographic wave is due to the reduction of hydrazono group of 4-(4'-sulphonamoyl)hydrazono-3-methyl-2-isoxazolin-5-

where R represents substituents (Tables 1 and 2).

Table 1. Electrochemical characteristics of 4-(4'-sulphonamoyl)hydrazono-3-methyl-2-isoxazolin-5-one*

pH = 6.9, concn. = 1.0×10^{-4} M

Sl. no.	R	$-E_{1/2}$ V	$\frac{dE_{1/2}}{dpH}$ -V/pH	i_d μA	αn_a	$I \times 10^{-4}$ $\mu A \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ mg}^{-2/3}$ $s^{-1/6}$	p	$D_0 \times 10^2$ $\text{cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$
1.		0.72	0.13	1.8	0.36	0.45	0.63	0.03
2.		0.82	0.16	2.0	0.28	0.50	0.59	0.04
3.		0.88	0.14	2.7	0.51	0.63	0.82	0.05
4.		0.87	0.12	2.6	0.28	0.65	0.58	0.05
5.		0.98	0.13	2.7	0.36	0.68	0.67	0.05

* $E_{1/2}$ = Half-wave potential, i_d = diffusion current, αn_a = product of transfer coefficient and number of electrons in the rate determining step, I = diffusion current constant, p = number of protons in rate determining step, D_0 = diffusion coefficient.

Table 2. Effect of solvent composition for 4-(4-guanyl sulphonamoyl)hydrazono-3-methyl-2-isoxazolin-5-one

Sl. no.	DMF %	NH	
		$-E_{1/2}$ V	i_d μA
1.	20	1.08	1.48
2.	30	1.10	1.24
3.	40	1.20	1.02
4.	50	1.22	0.82
5.	60	1.28	0.54
6.	70	1.26	0.23

in pH⁹ of the solution and an increase in the dissociation constant of the protonated species. Both these factors lower the extent of protonation and consequently would lead to the observed behaviour of $E_{1/2}$ and i_d .

Experimental

The stock solutions (1.0×10^{-3} M) of all the compounds (Table 1) were prepared in DMF. A 1.0 M KCl (A.R.) in double-distilled water was used as the supporting electrolyte. Britton-Robinson (BR) buffers (pH 2.5–11.0) were used to study the effect of pH on the electrode process.

Polarograms were scanned on an Elico CL 25 polarograph with capillary characteristics of $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 3.62 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{1/6}$ and $h = 67 \text{ cm}$. A saturated calomel electrode was used as the reference electrode. Solutions for polarographic/cyclic voltammetric measurements were prepared by mixing stock solution (1 ml) of the compound, DMF (2.0 ml, to prevent precipitation), 1.0 M KCl (1.0 ml) and BR buffer (6.0 ml), and polarograms were recorded after removal of oxygen and current was corrected for the residual current.

Cyclic voltammogram was scanned on a BAS CV-27 instrument, the details of which are described elsewhere¹⁰.

Controlled potential electrolysis (CPE) of the parent compound (A) was carried out at a plateau potential corresponding to the reduction of hydrazono group¹¹. Coulometric studies¹² were carried out using GC electrode at a potential by taking the stock solution (2.0 ml) of the compound, 1.0 M KCl (1 ml), DMF (2 ml) and buffer (5 ml). From decrease of current with time during electrolysis, the number of electrons transferred was calculated. Progress of electrolysis was monitored by recording waves/peaks at different intervals of time.

References

- O. Okimoto and T. Chiba, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1990, **55**, 1070; P. R. Reddy and A. B. Rao, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 1996, **12**, 534; N. C. Mathur, R. N. Goyal and W. U. Malik, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, **29**, 765; R. Jain, D. D. Agarwal and R. K. Shrivastava, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1990, 1353.
- L. Meits, "Polarographic Techniques", Interscience, New York, 1967.
- A. J. Bard and L. R. Faulkner, "Electrochemical Methods: Fundamentals and Applications", Wiley, 1980.
- R. S. Nicholson, *Anal. Chem.*, 1965, **37**, 1351.
- P. Zuman and C. I. Perrin, "Organic Polarography", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1969; P. Zuman, "The Elucidation of Organic Electrode Processes", Academic, New York, 1967.
- P. Zuman, "Substituents Effect in Organic Polarography", Plenum Press, New York, 1967.
- R. Jain, D. D. Agarwal, P. Pandey and R. K. Shrivastava, *Croat. Chem. Acta*, 1991, **64**, 607.
- P. Delahay, "Double Layer and Electrode Kinetics", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1966.
- K. Schwabe, "Advances in Polarography", Pergamon, London, 1960, Vol. III.
- R. Jain, S. Gupta and S. Tomar, *Electrochem. Soc. India*, 1998, **47**, 18.
- H. Lund, "Lecture at XIX Congress of Pure and Applied Chemistry", London, 1963.
- O. Manousek, O. Exner and P. Zuman, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1968, **33**, 3988.